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Glossary, abbreviations and acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
AGCM	Autorità Garante della Concorrenza e del Mercato
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ESR / ESRs	Early Stage Researcher(s)
INDRA	Indra Sistemas S.A.
JU	Jagiellonian University
LeADS	Legality Attentive Data Scientists
SSSA	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna
TELLU	Tellu IoT AS
TILL / TILLs	Technological Innovations in Law Laboratory (workshops)
UL	University of Luxembourg
UPRC	University of Piraeus Research Center
UT3	Université Toulouse 3
VUB	Vrije Universiteit Brussel
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is the accompanying report of the promotional video about the Technological Innovations in Law Laboratory (TILL) workshops. The TILLs have been designed within the LeADS project to provide dynamic and interactive workshops convened with the purpose of facilitating a dialogue between non-academic partners and early-stage researchers (ESRs) regarding innovations that intersect with regulatory, legal, and ethical frameworks. The focus is on addressing specific challenges and exploring effective solutions with a critical, hands-on approach, grounded in a multi-faceted understanding of the issue at hand. TILLs encourage critical appraisal skills, foster knowledge transfer to stakeholders, and aim to bridge the gap between theoretical research and practical business applications.

Overview

Technology Innovation in Law Laboratories (TILLs) within the LeADS training program is an idea that goes beyond the conventional learning practices and focuses on horizontal interactions and collaborative learning. TILLs aimed to prepare the ESRs for their secondments (at companies and regulators) in terms of knowledge transfer and in a more general pedagogical context seeking to reconcile the different vocabularies and practices around technology and law. UPRC as the Dissemination Manager recorded the activities of the ESRs, organised interviews with the moderators and the non-academic partners during the TILLs workshops and composed a promotional video to be disseminated through the project's channels (e.g. website and social media channels) which is also documented in the D2.4 Video about the TILLs.

The Video Content

The video is guided by a descriptive narration part following the subsequent order:

1. Introduction by the Project Coordinator (SSSA)

The coordinator of the LeADS project opens the video with a comprehensive introduction to the objectives of the LeADS project. This is followed by a high-level overview of the TILLs, explaining their significance in fostering innovation at the crossroads of law, policy, and technology. **(Video minutes: 00:07 - 02:25)**

2. Detailed Overview by TILLs Organizers (UL and VUB)

minutes: The main organizer from the University of Luxembourg (UL) provides an in-depth explanation of the preparation and organization of the TILLs. The organizer elaborates on the methodology and approach employed during the workshops to facilitate effective learning and engagement. **(Video minutes: 02:29 - 09:24)**

The co-organizer from the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB) presents an introduction to the three use cases analysed in the TILLs 1-2. This segment includes general information about the process and how these cases contribute to the objectives of the TILLs workshops. **(Video minutes: 09:25 - 11:45)**

3. Use Cases Overview

Non-academic partner AGCM representative, discusses the organization and introduces a specific use case that has been proposed for the ESRs. This portion of the video is dedicated to presenting the context and relevance of the AGCM challenge. **(Video minutes: 11:50 - 16:58)**

Non-academic partner TELLU representative outlines the company's role and presents a specific use case developed for the ESRs. The narrative focuses on the unique challenges and opportunities TELLU brings to the TILL workshops. **(Video minutes: 17:02 - 19:29)**

Non-academic partner INDRA introduce their company and detail the specific use case they have contributed to the TILLS. The video illustrates the practical implications of the INDRA case study for the ESRs. **(Video minutes: 19:30 - 20:49)**

4. Feedback on the introduced Use Cases by Moderators

minutes: Beneficiary and moderator from UL, serving as one of the mentors for the INDRA use case, provides constructive feedback on the ESRs' work. The mentor evaluates the solutions and insights developed by the ESRs in response to the INDRA challenge. **(Video minutes: 20:50 - 21:44)**

In the concluding segment, beneficiary, and moderator from JU, acting as a mentor for the AGCM use case, shares her feedback on the performance and problem-solving abilities demonstrated by the ESRs in addressing the AGCM use case. **(Video minutes: 21:50 - 22:47)**

The video can be found for download in high resolution in this [link](#). Lastly, the video has been published in the communication channels of the project as presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Communication Channel	Link
YouTube	https://youtu.be/CS5wkc8zMPU
Project Website	https://www.legalityattentivedatascientists.eu/2024/04/30/tills-video-available-on-youtube/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/LeADSmsca
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/leadmsca/

Conclusions

The promotional video about the Technological Innovations in Law Laboratory (TILL) workshops, as described in this deliverable report, successfully highlights the innovative approach and impactful outcomes of the TILLS within the LeADS project. The video serves as a comprehensive visual and narrative documentation of the dynamic and interactive workshops aimed at bridging the gap between academic research and practical business applications in technology, law, and policy disciplines. In particular, the video outlines specific use cases discussed during the workshops, such as those presented by project partners (AGCM, TELLU, and INDRA). Those use cases illustrate how the TILLS facilitate practical problem-solving and the application of theoretical knowledge in real-world scenarios, thereby validating the effectiveness of the workshops in producing tangible outcomes. Moreover, the TILLS serve as a platform that oversteps traditional educational formats by integrating multidisciplinary perspectives and fostering collaborative learning. The promotional video has been effectively disseminated through multiple channels including YouTube, the project website, and social media platforms like Twitter and LinkedIn, ensuring wide accessibility and outreach. This strategic dissemination enhances the visibility of the LeADS project's contributions to the academic and professional communities. To conclude, D2.4 effectively captures and communicates the essence and impact of the TILLS workshops within the LeADS project. It highlights the project's commitment to promote innovation and practical problem-solving, making a significant contribution to both academic research and practical applications in the fields of technology, law and policy. The promotional video not only serves as a proof of the success of the TILLS but also as a valuable tool for ongoing outreach and engagement with the various stakeholders and communities.

